

1st Vegetable Science Congress on Emerging Challenges in Vegetable Research and Education (VEGCON-2019)

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Abstracts

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the different phytophagous aphids, green peach aphid, *Myzus persicae* Sulz., black bean aphid, *Aphis craccivora* Koch. and mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) are dominant in vegetable ecosystem and are occurred one or another vegetables. To minimize the indiscriminate uses of pesticides hazards, some newer insecticide molecules with diverse mode of actions and green chemistry against these nefarious sucking pests in the vegetable ecosystem were evaluated by direct spray method under Potter's tower at 340 g cm² pressure so that development of possible resistance, if any, can be minimized. Amongst the newer molecules, Acetamiprid 20% SP was the most toxic against all the three vegetable aphid species with median lethal concentrations (LC₅₀) of 0.086, 0.545 and 1.84 ppm against *A. craccivora*, *M. persicae* and *L. erysimi*, respectively. Differential responses of aphids towards the test insecticides were observed. *A. craccivora* was the most susceptible one followed by *M. persicae* and *L. erysimi*. A comparison of LC₅₀ values for the commonly used and recommended insecticides determined over eight years revealed a shift in susceptibility to Imidacloprid, Thiamethoxam and Dimethoate where *M. persicae* showed 5.90, 2.51 and 2.72 fold resistance to these insecticides, respectively.

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Biodiversity and Geo-Mapping of Cucurbits Pest Species in Arid Region of Rajasthan

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Survey for biodiversity and geo-mapping of cucurbits pest species survey was conducted at different district of Rajasthan (Jodhpur, Pali, Sirohi, Udaipur, Chittorgarh, Kota, Bara, Bundi, Tonk, Jaipur, Sikar, Bikaner) during 2013-14 and 2014-15. The fruit fly incidence was ranged from 20 to 59 percent in cucurbits in surveyed area of Rajasthan. The incidence of red pumpkin beetle was found very high ranged from 5 to 74 percent in surveyed area of Rajasthan, in which southern Rajasthan found more incidence of red pumpkin and very less incidence was found in Northern Rajasthan. The incidence of hadda beetle was high in north part of Rajasthan and very less incidence in southern part of Rajasthan. For the first time, beet armyworm was observed in cucurbits in the hot arid region of north-western India, (i.e., Thar Desert) and identified as *Spodoptera exigua*. Beet armyworm is a polyphagous pest and serious pest of ridge gourd cause to leaves, flowers and fruits of plants. Smaller larvae devour the parenchyma of leaves, so all that remains is the thin epidermis and veins. Larger larvae tend to burrow holes through thick areas of plants. Ridge gourd fruits are most susceptible to injury, starting from young fruit to maturity of fruits. The beet armyworm is damage to summer as well as rainy season but more incidences was recorded in the rainy season crop. I have recoded and identified the incidence of pests like, aphid, white fly, leaf minor, surface grasshopper, bottle gourd bug, *Metacanthus pulchellus* and natural enemies like, carabid beetle, coccinellids like *Coccinella septempunctata*, *Cheilomenes sexmaculata*, *Scymnus coccivora*, praying mantid, green lace wings, *Chrysoperla carnia* and hadda beetle parasitoid, *Pediobius foveolatus*. The incidence of beetles, *Mylabris macilenta*, *Anthicus crinitus* and *Anthrenus subclaviger* on cucurbits flowers were also recorded during survey.

Key words: Cucurbits, fruit fly, hadda beetle, leaf eating caterpillar, arid region.